

Finding Top-K Preferable Products for Customer-Oriented Marketing Based on the Outranking Approach: A Case Study on Mexican Restaurants

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Abstract: Customer-oriented marketing is a strategy that aims to recommend the right product(s) to the right customer(s). It is low-cost, low-risk, and profit-driven. It typically involves two components: customers and products. One of the critical challenges of targeted marketing is identifying products with potential market value for customers. In this paper, we studied an instance of this general problem. This paper finds the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) from a set of products under study to be offered to a customer for targeted marketing. We model the k -MPP problem as a multicriteria ranking problem and propose an algorithmic framework for customer-oriented marketing. Our framework utilizes a multicriteria outranking approach to solve the k -MPP problem. The framework's effectiveness is demonstrated by conducting a case study to find the k -most preferable restaurants for a customer in a Mexican city.

Keywords: Targeted marketing, customer-oriented marketing strategy, multicriteria decision analysis, outranking approach, ELECTRE III method, information retrieval

Categories: H.4.2, J.1, J.7

DOI: 10.3897/jucs.150597

1 Introduction

Targeted marketing is a pivotal strategy in today's competitive market, focusing on identifying and reaching groups of customers with specific products that match their preferences and needs. This approach has been shown to improve customer engagement and increase the effectiveness of marketing efforts by recommending the right products to the right customers [Ling and Li, 1998; Sarkar and De Bruyn, 2021]. Despite its potential, one of the persistent challenges in targeted marketing is accurately identifying the products that hold the highest potential value for customers. This challenge, known as the customer-oriented targeted marketing problem, involves selecting a small, relevant set of products from a vast pool to be recommended to a specific customer or group of customers [Ferguson et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2005]. This problem is also known as a product recommendation problem [Adomavicius and Tuzhilin, 2005; Hao et al., 2020]. Identifying exciting products for a customer with potential purchase value by the customer is one of the critical problems in targeted marketing [Huang et al.,

2014; Bijmolt et al., 2021], and diverse researchers have investigated finding the top- k preferable products [Yang et al., 2023; Islam and Liu, 2016; Shambour et al., 2023].

Existing methods for customer-oriented marketing, such as collaborative and content-based filtering, have been widely adopted. Collaborative filtering leverages transaction data to recommend products based on the preferences of like-minded customers, while content-based filtering uses product attributes to match products to customer preferences [Adomavicius and Tuzhilin, 2005; Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2024]. Several methods are available to enhance a recommender system's performance [Shambour et al., 2023]. A common solution combines collaborative and content-based filtering techniques using customer profiles, product profiles, and transaction data [Javed et al., 2021; Villegas et al., 2018]. However, these methods often fall short in scenarios where customer preferences are complex and multifaceted, particularly when decisions must be made across multiple criteria. As a result, these approaches can lead to suboptimal recommendations, limiting their effectiveness in truly capturing customer preferences.

The motivation and necessity for solving the customer-oriented marketing problem using a multicriteria outranking approach are rooted in the complexity and variability of customer preferences and the limitations of traditional methods in effectively capturing these nuances. On the one hand, customers often have diverse and multifaceted preferences that simple or single-criterion methods cannot adequately capture. Traditional recommender systems may struggle to account for customers' subtle trade-offs between product attributes (e.g., price vs. quality, brand vs. feature set). The multicriteria outranking approach allows for incorporating multiple criteria that reflect these diverse preferences. It can model the relative importance of each criterion and how customers prioritize different aspects of products, leading to a more accurate and personalized recommendation.

On the other hand, in real-world scenarios, customer preferences may not be fully known or may change over time, leading to incomplete or inconsistent data. The multicriteria outranking approach can handle such situations by comparing alternatives even with partial information. Also, traditional methods like collaborative or content-based filtering often produce results that are difficult to interpret or justify from a decision-making perspective. The multicriteria outranking approach offers a structured and transparent method for understanding why certain products are recommended over others. This transparency is critical when the recommendations must be justified or explained to customers or stakeholders.

In this research work, we have recognized this limitation and responded by exploring multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) techniques to enhance the precision of product recommendations. MCDA offers a structured approach to decision-making that considers multiple criteria, making it well-suited for applications in customer-oriented marketing [Roy, 1996]. However, despite the potential of MCDA, there remains a significant gap in its application to the specific problem of identifying the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) for targeted marketing. Most existing studies have not fully explored the integration of MCDA with targeted marketing strategies to develop a comprehensive framework that effectively addresses this problem [Ivan Franko et al., 2021; Rosário and Raimundo, 2021; Alves Gomes and Meisen, 2023].

With the growing volume of products and services available in markets, identifying the top- k most preferable products for a specific customer becomes increasingly

challenging. The multicriteria outranking approach offers a systematic way to sift through a large pool of products and identify those that best match the customer's preferences, improving the efficiency and effectiveness of targeted marketing efforts. This approach is particularly necessary in competitive markets where the ability to offer highly personalized recommendations can be a key differentiator. Customers often make decisions based on a combination of factors, such as price, quality, brand, and features. A multicriteria outranking approach is necessary to balance these factors appropriately. It provides a way to simultaneously consider all relevant criteria and rank products to reflect the customer's preferences rather than focusing on one aspect. This is crucial when no criterion adequately captures the customer's decision-making process. The multicriteria outranking approach is flexible and can be adapted to different decision-making contexts, making it a versatile tool in customer-oriented marketing. Whether the context is e-commerce, restaurant recommendations, or any other product/service offering, this approach can be tailored to meet specific needs, making it necessary for businesses that operate in diverse markets.

This paper seeks to fill this gap by proposing a novel algorithmic framework that integrates a multicriteria outranking approach with customer-oriented marketing strategies. The proposed framework is designed to model and rank products based on customer preferences, enabling greater accuracy in identifying the *k*-MPP. To demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach, the paper presents a case study focused on finding the *k*-most preferable restaurants for a customer in a Mexican city.

This paper is divided into six additional sections. [Section 2] presents background information. [Section 3] formulates the customer-oriented marketing problem. [Section 4] describes the proposed approach. [Section 5] discusses an outranking model for the customer-oriented marketing strategy. [Section 6] presents an illustrative example. Finally, conclusions and potential future work are presented in [Section 7].

2 Background Information

2.1 Targeted Marketing

In marketing, there are two main approaches to communication: mass marketing and targeted marketing (or direct marketing) [Camilleri, 2018] [Ling and Li, 1998]. Mass marketing involves using mass media, such as print, radio, and television, to reach a broad and diverse audience. It does not consider the characteristics or needs of individual customers.

On the other hand, targeted marketing is a marketing strategy that involves identifying customers with the potential for market value by studying their characteristics and needs. This approach aims to establish and maintain direct relationships between suppliers and buyers based on one or more product/market combinations. Targeted customers are selected for promotion based on their unique characteristics and needs in targeted marketing.

2.1.1 The Customer-Oriented Marketing Strategy

[Adomavicius and Tuzhilin, 2005] and [Huang et al., 2014] propose to define preference relations on a set of products P_m from the standing point of a customer, respectively, fixing either a customer or a product in this form.

Let us consider the outranking relation S_c on $P_m \times P_m$. For customer-oriented marketing, we focus on a particular customer c and define an outranking relation S_c onto P_m .

For a customer $c \in C$, we can define S_c onto P_m as follows

$p_i S_c p_j \leftrightarrow (c, p_i) S(c, p_j) \leftrightarrow$ for the customer c , product p_i outranks (is preferred or is indifferent) to product p_j .

According to S_c , we can compare products pairwise based on the customer's preferences. In so doing, we have a customer-oriented marketing strategy.

2.2 Preference Outranking Relations

Let $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\}$ be a set of alternatives and assume that defined criteria exist $g_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$. A criterion g_k , having indifference and preference thresholds q_k and p_k , respectively ($p_k \geq q_k \geq 0$), is called a pseudo-criterion. We use a veto threshold v_k ($v_k \geq p_k$) to model situations where a deficient assessment of an alternative a_j to a_i , according to some criterion g_k , cannot be compensated by a good evaluation of one or several other criteria.

We use outranking approaches to get a global preference model on the set of alternatives [Roy, 1996]. There are two phases: aggregation and exploitation.

2.3 Aggregation Phase

According to the global model of decision-maker's preferences, $a_i S a_j$ is true if there are sufficient reasons to declare that " a_i is at least as good as a_j " or " a_i is not worse than a_j ," and "there is no compelling reason to disprove such a statement."

Each pair of a_i and a_j alternatives is tested to check whether the assertion $a_i S a_j$ is valid. In the ELECTRE III outranking method [Roy, 1996], the test to accept an assertion $a_i S a_j$ is implemented using the concordance and non-discordance conditions:

Assuming all criteria are maximized, the k^{th} criterion is in concordance with assertion $a_i S a_j$ if and only if $g_k(a_i) \geq g_k(a_j) - q_k$. The k^{th} criterion is in discordance with the assertion $a_i S a_j$ if and only if $g_k(a_j) \geq g_k(a_i) + p_k$.

For every pair of alternatives $(a_i, a_j) \in A \times A$. Let w_k be the importance coefficient or weight for criterion k . We define a fuzzy outranking relation as follows:

$$C(a_i, a_j) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{k=1}^n w_k c_k(a_i, a_j), \quad \text{where } w = \sum_{k=1}^n w_k \tag{1}$$

where:

$$c_k(a_i, a_j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } g_k(a_i) + q_k \geq g_k(a_j) \\ 0, & \text{if } g_k(a_i) + p_k \leq g_k(a_j) \\ \frac{p_k + g_k(a_i) - g_k(a_j)}{p_k - q_k}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{2}$$

To calculate discordance, we define another threshold called the veto threshold. The veto threshold, v_k , allows for the possibility of $a_i \succ a_j$ to be refused totally if, for any one criterion k , $g_k(a_j) > g_k(a_i) + v_k$. The discordance index for each criterion k , $d_k(a_i, a_j)$ is calculated as follows:

$$d_k(a_i, a_j) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } g_k(a_i) + p_k \geq g_k(a_j) \\ 1, & \text{if } g_k(a_i) + v_k \leq g_k(a_j) \\ \frac{g_k(a_j) - g_k(a_i) - p_k}{v_k - p_k}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{3}$$

The credibility degree for each pair $(a_i, a_j) \in A \times A$ is defined as follows:

$$\sigma(a_i, a_j) = \begin{cases} C(a_i, a_j), & \text{if } K(a_i, a_j) = \varnothing \\ C(a_i, a_j) \cdot \prod_{k \in K(a_i, a_j)} \frac{1 - d_k(a_i, a_j)}{1 - C(a_i, a_j)}, & \text{if } K(a_i, a_j) \neq \varnothing \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

where $K(a_i, a_j)$ is the set of criteria such that $d_k(a_i, a_j) > C(a_i, a_j)$.

Therefore, we have constructed a fuzzy outranking relation S_A^σ defined on $A \times A$. This marks the completion of the outranking model. The next step is to use the model to rank alternatives based on the fuzzy outranking relation S_A^σ . Our exploitation approach uses the Net Flow Rule [Brans et al., 1986].

3 Formulation of the Customer-Oriented Marketing Problem

Suppose we have a large set of products $P_m = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$ of a company that a marketer can offer to a particular customer. The products can be analyzed by a family of criteria $G = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n\}$, where $g_j(p_i)$ denotes the assessment of the product p_i by criterion g_j .

The product set P_m can be decomposed into three subsets $P_m 1$, $P_m 2$, and $P_m 3$. $P_m 1$ is the set of products under study to be offered to the customer c , $P_m 2$ is the set of products of the company that the customer c has purchased at least once, and there are records of their purchases, and finally $P_m 3$ represents the set of products of the company which the customer has never bought them.

The customer-oriented targeted marketing problem consisted of:

- i) Modeling the aggregation preferences of the customer, represented by a fuzzy outranking relation, denoted as $S_{P_m}^\sigma (\sigma(p_i, p_j))$, which must be understood as the degree of strength of the arguments favoring the crisp outranking $p_i S_{P_m} p_j$, where $p_i S_{P_m} p_j$ means that the product p_i is at least as preferred as the product p_j to customer c or product p_i outranks product p_j to customer c .
- ii) Obtaining a partial order of products $O_{P_m}^*$ from $S_{P_m}^\sigma$ in decreasing order of preferences.
- iii) Defining a cut-off point of the partial order based on specific criteria.
- iv) Finding the intersection of the sets $P_m 1$ and the top-ranked portion of the partial order and choose them as the targeted products.

We want to find the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) $P_m 1$ for targeted marketing.

We model the k -MPP problem and propose an algorithmic framework for customer-oriented marketing. Our framework utilizes a multicriteria outranking approach to solve the k -MPP problem.

4 The Proposed Approach

The procedure's general scheme for ranking products comprises four main levels, as shown in [Fig. 1]. It aims to find the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) from $P_m 1$ as compatible as possible with the revealed preference information provided by the customer.

– *Level 1* is related to the initial input data, i.e., the set of products P_m , the set of customers C_t , the set of attributes H_n , the set of values V_{h_k} that takes an attribute

$h_k \in H_n$, an information function I_{h_k} , and the product profile table G_{P_m} .

– *Level 2* is related to the revealed preference information provided by the customer:

- 1. The transaction table $T_{C_t \times P_m}$.
- 2. Set of criteria G_n .
- 3. Performance matrix.

– *Level 3* is related to the aggregation phase, which aggregates partial preference relations derived from pairwise comparisons of products concerning each criterion into one or several global preference relations.

– *Level 4* processes the global preference relation to obtain the final ranking of products based on decreasing order of preferences. It is also defined as a cut-off point k on the ranking.

The procedure output produces the k -most preferred products (k -MPP) from P_m . If the decision-maker agrees with the conclusions, the procedure ends; otherwise, revise the input data or preference information.

Figure 1: General scheme of the procedure for obtaining a customer's preferred products (k -MPP) from P_m .

5 An Outranking Model for the Customer-Oriented Marketing Strategy

In the context of targeted marketing, the outranking relation S_c means the following:

$p_i S_c p_j \leftrightarrow$ for customer c , product p_i outranks (is preferred or is indifferent) to product p_j .

5.1 Construction of an Outranking Model and Deriving a Ranking

Product profiles and transaction data are given by information tables [Huang et al., 2014]. An information table is a quadruple:

$$IT = (P_m, H, \{V_{h_k} : h_k \in H\}, \{I_{h_k} : h_k \in H\})$$

where P_m is a finite nonempty set of products, H is a finite nonempty set of attributes, V_{h_k} is a nonempty set of values for $h_k \in H$, and $I_{h_k} : P_m \rightarrow V_{h_k}$ is an information function for $h_k \in H$.

We utilize two types of tables for customer-oriented marketing: the product profile table and the transaction table. The transaction table contains information about customer evaluations of various products. Each row in the table represents a customer's

judgments on different products, while each column represents the judgments of other customers on the same product.

The outranking relation is constructed by product pairwise comparisons based on the implicitly given customer's preferences. The outranking relation S_c can be exploited to derive a ranking of products. A cut-off point may be chosen based on specific criteria. We can select targeted products above the cut-off point. In the following, we explain in detail this strategy.

We can regard the product profile as the input of the outranking relation. For customer c , the outranking relation of products could be defined using the concordance and non-discordance conditions and the indifference, preference, and veto thresholds and weights as the parameters of the outranking relation model deduced from the customer's preferences.

The product set P_m can be decomposed into the three subsets $P_m 1$, $P_m 2$, and $P_m 3$. A discrete or continuous criterion function g_{h_k} can be deduced from the attribute h_k , for each $h_k \in H$, and it may be defined based on the historical distribution of attribute values. In the following, we detail the determination of these two types of criteria.

5.1.1 The Criterion g_{h_k} is Discrete

Suppose the set of attribute values V_{h_k} is discrete, and, let $r(v)$ be the subset of $P_m 2$ defined by $r(v) = \{p \in P_m 2 : I_{h_k}(p) = v, v \in V_{h_k}\}$. Let $|r(v)|$ represent the cardinality of the set $r(v)$. We define a frequentist version of the function f_{h_k} as

$$f_{h_k}(v) = \frac{|r(v)|}{\sum_{v' \in V_{h_k}} |r(v')|} = \frac{|r(v)|}{m_2}$$

where m_2 is the number of products in $P_m 2$.

In terms of products, we have an equivalent definition:

$$f_{h_k}(I_{h_k}(p)) = \frac{|r(I_{h_k}(p))|}{m_2}$$

The function g_{h_k} is defined as

$$g_k = g_{h_k} = f_{h_k} \circ I_{h_k} : P_m \rightarrow [0,1]$$

is a discrete criterion function deduced from the attribute h_k , for each $h_k \in H$ for which the set of attribute values V_{h_k} is discrete.

According to the functions f_{h_k} , an attribute value contributes more to the interest of a product if it is found in a greater number of products. Regarding MCDA, the set $P_m 1$ represents the set of decision alternatives under study, and the set $G = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n\}$ represents a family of decision criteria.

5.1.2 The Criterion g_{h_k} is Continuous

Now, Suppose the set of attribute values V_{h_k} is continuous. The set V_{h_k} represents a scale associated with $I_{h_k} : P_m \rightarrow V_{h_k}$, the information (performance) function for $h_k \in H$.

We will give some examples of preference continuous criteria that can appear in customer-oriented marketing. These continuous criteria are derived from types of attributes where the customer’s preferences range on an interval of real values of the attributes of the products that the customer has historically purchased:

Case 1. The customer expresses a weak preference for those products whose attribute value is between 0 and x_1 , while he (she) shows a strong preference for those whose attribute value is between x_1 and x_2 , and expresses a weak preference for those products with a value of the attribute between x_2 and x_3 . Any product whose attribute value is less than 0 and greater than x_3 is not attractive to the customer where $0 < x_1 < x_2 < x_3$. The behavior of this function can be modeled as a fuzzy trapezoidal function, as shown graphically in [Fig. 2], and algebraically through equation (5):

Figure 2: Trapezoidal fuzzy function to model customer preferences.

Source: Own elaboration.

$$g_{h_k}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x}{x_1} & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq x_1 \\ 1 & \text{if } x_1 \leq x \leq x_2 \\ \frac{x_3 - x}{x_3 - x_2} & \text{if } x_2 \leq x \leq x_3 \\ 0 & \text{if } x > x_3 \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Case 2. The customer expresses a strong preference for those products whose attribute value is up to x_1 , while he (she) shows a weak preference for those whose attribute value is between x_1 and x_2 . Any product whose attribute value is greater than x_2 is not attractive to the customer, where $0 < x_1 < x_2$. The behavior of this function can be

modeled as a fuzzy trapezoidal function opened to the left side, as shown graphically in [Fig. 3], and algebraically through equation (6):

Figure 3: The trapezoidal fuzzy function opened to the left side to model a client's preferences on a specific attribute. Source: Own elaboration.

$$g_{h_k}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq x_1 \\ \frac{x_2 - x}{x_2 - x_1} & \text{if } x_1 \leq x \leq x_2 \\ 0 & \text{if } x > x_2 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Case 3. The customer expresses a weak preference for those products whose attribute value is from 0 to x_1 , while he (she) shows a strong preference for those products whose attribute value is equal or greater to x_1 , where $0 < x_1$. The behavior of this function can be modeled as a fuzzy trapezoidal function opened to the right side, as shown graphically in [Fig. 4], and algebraically through equation (7):

Figure 4: The fuzzy trapezoidal function is open to the right side to model a client's preferences on a specific attribute. Source: Own elaboration.

$$g_{h_k}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x}{x_1} & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq x_1 \\ 1 & \text{if } x \geq x_1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Therefore, it can be defined that a product p_i is preferable to a product p_j or “at least as good as” if $g_{h_k}(p_i) \geq g_{h_k}(p_j)$, where $g_{h_k}(p_i)$ is the preference degree of the attribute h_k within a product p_i . The decision-maker is interested in modeling strong customer preferences for purchases based on a specific attribute. Then, it should be desirable to offer the customer products whose attribute value range is in the category of strong preference modeling according to their pattern of historical product purchases in the company. All these criteria are to maximize. Generally, a trapezoidal fuzzy function can have various shapes depending on the application. Note that these three cases are not exhaustive, and more different cases can be modeled according to the customer's preference behavior.

Example 1. Modeling customer preferences with continuous criteria

Consider the scenario where a customer has shown a preference for products within a specific price range. For instance, the customer might express a weak preference for products priced between \$10 and \$20, a strong preference for those between \$20 and \$30, and a weak preference for those priced between \$30 and \$40. Products priced below \$10 or above \$40 might not interest this customer. This preference can be graphically represented using a fuzzy trapezoidal function, which captures the varying degrees of preference across different price ranges. Mathematically, this preference can be modeled using a fuzzy trapezoidal function as follows:

$$g_{h_k}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq 10 \\ \frac{x-10}{10} & \text{if } 10 < x \leq 20 \\ 1 & \text{if } 20 < x \leq 30 \\ \frac{40-x}{10} & \text{if } 30 < x \leq 40 \\ 0 & \text{if } x > 40 \end{cases}$$

Here, the function g_{h_k} increases linearly as the price moves from \$10 to \$20, reaches its peak between \$20 and \$30, and then decreases as the price moves beyond \$30.

Example 2. Handling continuous data for distance criterion

Another example involves a customer's preference based on the distance to a restaurant. Suppose a customer prefers restaurants that are close to their location, with a strong preference for those within 5 kilometers and a weak preference for those between 5 and 10 kilometers. Restaurants further than 10 kilometers away are not preferred. This scenario can also be modeled using a fuzzy trapezoidal function:

$$g_{h_k}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 5 \\ \frac{10-x}{5} & \text{if } 5 \leq x \leq 10 \\ 0 & \text{if } x > 10 \end{cases}$$

This function g_{h_k} captures the gradual decline in preference as the distance from the customer's location increases.

These fuzzy trapezoidal functions are crucial in MCDA because they allow for the incorporation of continuous customer preferences into the decision-making process. For instance, when evaluating multiple restaurants for a recommendation, the system can assign scores based on how well each restaurant's distance aligns with the customer's preference profile. The restaurants closest to the customer's ideal distance will receive higher scores, making them more likely to be recommended.

5.1.3 The Outranking Model and the Associated Ranking

In the following, we propose an algorithmic framework for customer-oriented marketing, finding the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) from P_m for targeted marketing. Our framework utilizes a multicriteria outranking approach to solve the k -MPP problem.

Step 1. Essential elements of the MCDA problem.

This step defines the set of products $P_m = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$ that a marketer can offer to a particular customer. The products are characterized by a set of criteria $G = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n\}$.

Step 2. Decomposition of the product set P_m . $P_m = \bigcup_{i=1}^3 P_m^i$, $\{P_m^i, P_m^j\}$ are pairwise disjuncts, $i \neq j$, $i, j = 1, 2, 3$.

Step 3. Determination of the performance matrix. The customer provides for each alternative p_i and each criterion g_k their assessment $g_k(p_i)$ in a numerical domain.

Step 4. Determination of weights denoted by w_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, with $w_k > 0$ for each $g_k \in G$, and $\sum_{g_k \in G} w_k = 1$, and the indifference $q_k(p_i)$, preference $p_k(p_i)$, and veto $v_k(p_i)$ thresholds for each criterion $g_k \in G$ where for consistency reasons $v_k > p_k \geq q_k \geq 0$.

Step 5. For each criterion g_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, compute the indifference (I_k), strict preference (P_k), weak preference (Q_k), and partial outranking S_k ($S_k = P_k \cup Q_k \cup I_k$) relations.

Step 6. Determination of the coalitions $C(p_i I p_j)$, $C(p_i P p_j)$, and $C(p_i Q p_j)$.

Each represents the set of criteria such that $p_i I_k p_j$, $p_i P_k p_j$, and $p_i Q_k p_j$, respectively.

Step 7. For each pair of products $(p_i, p_j) \in P_m 1 \times P_m 1$, compute a concordance index $c(p_i, p_j)$.

Step 8. For each pair of products $(p_i, p_j) \in P_m 1 \times P_m 1$, and for each criterion $g_k \in G$, compute a criterion discordance index $d_k(p_i, p_j)$.

Step 9. For each pair of products $(p_i, p_j) \in P_m 1 \times P_m 1$, Compute the credibility index $\sigma(p_i, p_j)$ ($0 \leq \sigma(p_i, p_j) \leq 1$), and construct a fuzzy outranking relation $S_{P_m}^\sigma$.

Step 10. Compute the leaving and entering flows $\varphi^+(p_i)$, $\varphi^-(p_i)$ for each $(p_i, p_j) \in P_m 1 \times P_m 1$

Step 11. Compute the net flow $\varphi(p_i)$ and induce a complete ranking of the products of $P_m 1$.

Step 12. Define a cut-off point of the ranking based on specific criteria.

Step 13. Find the intersection of the sets $P_m 1$ and the top-ranked portion of the ranking and choose them as the targeted products.

With this algorithmic framework for customer-oriented marketing, we find the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) from $P_m 1$ for targeted marketing. Our framework utilizes a multicriteria outranking approach to solve the k -MPP problem.

5.2 Added Value of the Proposed Outranking Model for Solving the Customer-Oriented Marketing Problem

The added value of this proposal can be considered from two perspectives: recommender systems and a multicriteria outranking approach. Both approaches aim to recommend the most suitable products to customers based on their preferences, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of targeted marketing. The goal is to ensure that the products suggested to the customer align closely with their specific preferences and past behaviors.

From the recommender system perspective, the proposed outranking model enriches recommender systems by incorporating multicriteria decision analysis into the traditional recommendation framework. Unlike conventional recommender systems, which primarily rely on collaborative filtering or content-based filtering, this approach considers multiple criteria simultaneously, offering a more nuanced and tailored product recommendation. The proposed model can more accurately calculate customer preferences by using customer profiles, product profiles, and transaction data. This leads to higher satisfaction rates, as the recommendations are more closely aligned with the customer's specific needs and preferences. Also, the method goes beyond simple preference calculation by creating a personalized ranking of products for each customer. This addresses the common problem of information overload in recommendation systems by focusing on the most relevant products, thus improving the customer's decision-making experience.

From the multicriteria outranking perspective, using outranking relations allows the model to handle complex preference structures. It incorporates indifference, preference, and veto thresholds, enabling the model to differentiate between subtle preference nuances that other models might overlook. It is important to note that the outranking approach does not require a single criterion to dominate the decision-making process. Instead, it considers the overall strength of preference across multiple criteria, providing a more balanced and equitable ranking of products. The proposed framework can be adapted to different decision contexts by adjusting the criteria, weights, and thresholds. This makes it suitable for a wide range of marketing scenarios.

6 An Illustrative Example

In this section, we apply the previously described algorithmic framework for customer-oriented marketing to address the specific problem of identifying the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) in the context of targeted marketing. To showcase our approach, we conducted a case study in a Mexican city to find the k -most preferred restaurants for a customer.

6.1 Selection and Composition of the Database

The case study relied on a database gathered from an online restaurant guide [Vargas et al., 2011]. Containing 138 users contributing ratings of 130 restaurants, the database centers on three urban areas in Mexico: San Luis Potosí and Soledad de Graciano in the state of San Luis Potosí; Cuernavaca and Jiutepec in the state of Morelos; and Ciudad Victoria in Tamaulipas. The data used in this case study can be accessed at: <https://doi.org/10.24432/C5DP41>.

6.2 Database Table Classification

The tables within the database can be grouped into three categories as follows:

- 1) Restaurant Data: {Restaurants, Accepted Payment Methods, Cuisines, Opening Hours, Parking Information},
- 2) User Data: {User Profiles, User Payment Methods, Preferred Cuisine Types}
- 3) Transactional Data: {User Ratings of Restaurants}

For this case study, we utilized the restaurant data tables (group 1) and specifically extracted geographical information from group 2's user profiles. This geographical information was then employed to calculate the selected user's distance to various restaurants. The rating table was also exclusively used to identify the restaurants each user had visited. For this study, we chose user U1061 due to the convenience of being the user who had visited the most restaurants, thus providing the most substantial information for our model.

6.3 Formulation of the Restaurant Recommendation Problem

To contextualize the restaurant recommendation problem within the framework of targeted marketing, users are treated as customers, restaurants are viewed as products, and the user-restaurant relations expressed in the rating table are considered the transaction table. In this context, the problem involves exploiting restaurant information and a user's visit records to construct an outranking relation, ultimately facilitating personalized restaurant recommendations that align with the principles of customer-oriented marketing.

Suppose we have a large set of restaurants $P_m = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$ that marketers of an online guide can offer to a particular user. The restaurants can be represented by a set of attributes $H = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n\}$, which can be analyzed by a family of criteria $G = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n\}$, where $g_j(p_i)$ represents the evaluation of the restaurant p_i by criteria g_j . The restaurants set P_m can be decomposed into three subsets $P_m 1$, $P_m 2$, and $P_m 3$. $P_m 1$ is the set of restaurants under study to be offered to the customer c , $P_m 2$ is the set of restaurants that the user c has visited at least once, and there are records of its visits and finally $P_m 3$ represents the set of restaurants in the guide that marketers do not want to offer to user c , based on a priori judgments, this set can be void.

6.3.1 Alternatives

The solution alternatives for the restaurant recommendation problem are the restaurants of the subset $P_m 1$.

6.3.2 Attributes

The attributes used to characterize restaurants can be divided into two groups depending on the values they can take: continuous attributes and discrete attributes.

6.3.2.1 Discrete Attributes

- *Alcohol*: Indicates if the restaurant offers alcoholic beverages and the type of beverages served. The attribute levels are:
 - {Full_bar, Not_served, Wine and beer}
- *Smoking_area*: Indicates if the restaurant has a smoking area. The attribute levels are:
 - {Not allowed, Only_in_bar, Permitted, Smoking_area}
- *Dress_code*: Indicates the restaurant's code. The attribute levels are:
 - {Casual, Formal, Informal}
- *Accessibility*: Describes the level of accessibility for disabled people. The attribute levels are:
 - {No accessibility, Partial, Complete}

- *Price*: Indicates the restaurant's value. The values that the attribute can take are:
 - {Low, Medium, High}
- *Ambiance*: Describes the type of atmosphere the restaurant has. The attribute levels are:
 - {Familiar, Quiet}
- *Franchise*: Indicates if the restaurant is a franchise. The values this attribute can take are:
 - {f = false, t = true}
- *Area*: Describes what the restaurant area is like, open or closed. Levels are:
 - {Open, Closed}
- *Card_payment*: Describes whether you accept card payments. The levels you can take are:
 - {0 = does not accept card payment, 1 = accepts card payment}
- *Rcuisine*: Describe the type of food served at the restaurant. It can be one of the following values or combinations thereof:
 - {American, Asian, Hamburger, Café, Cuban, ..., Mexica}
- *Hours*: Restaurant opening hours, weekdays (Monday to Friday), Saturdays, and Sundays. In the range of 0 to 23:59 hours. The opening hours were summarized as morning, afternoon, and night.
- *Parking*: Describes the type of parking that the restaurant has, and can take the following levels:
 - {None = no parking, Public = public parking, Valet parking = valet parking, Yes = private parking}

6.3.2.2 Continuous Attribute

- *Distance*: It is the distance measured in Kilometers from the user's location to the restaurant location calculated with the haversine formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Distance} = & \cos^{-1}[\cos(90 - \text{User Latitude}) \\
 & \cdot \cos(90 - \text{Restaurant Latitude}) \\
 & + \sin(90 - \text{User Latitude}) \\
 & \cdot \sin(90 - \text{Restaurant Latitude}) \\
 & \cdot \cos(\text{User Longitude} - \text{Restaurant Longitude})] \\
 & \cdot (6371)
 \end{aligned}$$

Note: The calculations of the trigonometric functions were performed in radians.

6.4 User Preference Elicitation

6.4.1 Decision Criteria

For this case study, decision criteria were created from the attributes of the restaurants, following the guidelines previously presented in [Section 5.1].

6.4.1.1 Decision Criteria for Discrete Attributes

For the discrete attributes indicated in [Section 6.3.2.1], decision criteria were constructed using the equations in [Section 5.1.1], and all criteria are to be maximized. [Tab. 1] below shows the attributes' values and the associated criteria.

Decision criteria for discrete attributes				
Attributes	Attributes values	Frequency in $P_m 2$	Value g_i	Criteria
alcohol	no alcohol served	12	0.667	g_1
	wine-beer	4	0.222	
	full bar	2	0.111	
smoking area	not allowed	15	0.833	g_2
	section	3	0.167	
	only_at_bar	0	0	
dress code	allowed	0	0	g_3
	informal	16	0.889	
	casual	2	0.111	
accessibility	formal	0	0	g_4
	no accessibility	10	0.556	
	full	6	0.333	
price	partial	2	0.111	g_5
	medium	9	0.500	
	low	6	0.333	
franchise	high	3	0.167	g_6
	family-friendly	16	0.889	
	quiet	2	0.111	
ambience	False	13	0.722	g_7
	True	5	0.278	
area	Closed	16	0.889	g_8
	Open	2	0.111	
accepts card payment	Yes	10	0.556	g_9
	No	8	0.444	

Attributes	Attributes values	Frequency in $P_m 2$	Value g_i	Criteria
cuisine type	Mongolian	4	0.222	g_{10}
	Bar_Pub_Brewery	2	0.111	
	Armenian	1	0.056	
	Bar_Pub_Brewery, Barbecue	1	0.056	
	Bar_Pub_Brewery, California	1	0.056	
	Barbecue	1	0.056	
	Burgers	1	0.056	
	Cafe-Coffee Shop, Fine Dining	1	0.056	
	California	1	0.056	
	Fine Dining	1	0.056	
	Juice	1	0.056	
	Not Available	1	0.056	
	Polish	1	0.056	
	Soup	1	0.056	
	Armenian, German	0	0	
Bar, California	0	0		
Cafe-Coffee Shop	0	0		
Cafeteria, California	0	0		
California, Continental-European	0	0		
California, Fine Dining, Polish	0	0		
Contemporary	0	0		
Continental-European	0	0		
Fine Dining, Polish	0	0		
Italian	0	0		
Japanese	0	0		
Opening Hours	WD: m,a,n; Sat: m, a, n; Sun: m, a, n	8	0.444	g_{11}
	WD: m, a; Sat: m, a, n; Sun: m, a, n	3	0.167	
	WD: a,n; Sat: a, n; Sun: a, n	2	0.111	
	WD: m, a; Sat: m, a; Sun: m, a	1	0.056	
	WD: m,a,n; Sat: m, a; Sun: m, a	1	0	
	WD: m; Sat: m; Sun: m	1	0	
	WD: a,n; Sat: a, n; Sun: c	1	0.056	
	WD: a,n; Sat: a, n; Sun: a	1	0.056	
	WD: m, a; Sat: m, a; Sun: c	0	0.000	
	WD: m,a,n; Sat: m, a, n; Sun: c	0	0.000	
WD: m,a,n; Sat: m, a, n; Sun: m, a	0	0		
WD: n; Sat: n; Sun: a, n	0	0.000		
parking	no parking	9	0.500	g_{12}
	paid parking	6	0.333	
	public parking	3	0.167	
	valet parking	0	0	

Table 1: Decision criteria for discrete attributes. Own elaboration

6.4.1.2 Decision Criteria for the Continuous Attribute Distance

To define the criteria associated with the distance attribute, first, we observe the behavior of the distances of restaurants in $P_m 2$, which we can review in the following table:

Restaurants Distances			
Restaurant ID	Distance in Km	Restaurant ID	Distance in Km
135041	4.321	135048	6.381
132825	4.778	135026	6.651
132834	5.278	135046	6.761
132921	5.449	135058	7.157
132754	5.550	132955	7.557
135075	5.588	135086	7.894
132954	5.677	132958	8.400
132572	5.707	132723	8.552
135080	6.267	135034	8.662

Table 2: Distance in kilometers from user U1061. Own elaboration

[Tab. 2] indicates that user U1061 has visited restaurants between 4.321 and 8.662 kilometers. These preferences can be represented through a fuzzy trapezoidal function, as illustrated in [Fig. 3] and described by Equation 6 in [Section 5.1.2]. This function takes x_1 and x_2 values as reference where $0 < x_1 < x_2$; and expresses the customer preferences in the distance criteria as follows:

- Strongly prefers restaurants with a distance between 0 and x_1 .
- There is a weak preference for restaurants with distances between x_1 and x_2
- There is no preference for restaurants with distances greater than x_2 .

The value of x_2 is determined trivially, with the greatest distance from the restaurants visited by user U1061 (8.662 km).

To find x_1 we estimate the kernel density of the distances of the restaurants visited by user U1061. To do this, we use the Epanechnikov kernel and a bandwidth of two times the average of the distance differences between the restaurants ordered from smallest to greatest (bandwidth = 0.5107). We will assign to x_1 the value of the distance of the first restaurant that exceeds the penultimate local maximum of the kernel density estimation function.

[Fig. 5] shows the kernel density estimation for the distances of the restaurants visited by user U1061. The red dotted line marks the location of the penultimate local maximum:

Figure 5: Kernel density estimation for the distances of restaurants visited by user U1061

[Tab. 3] shows the values of x_1 and x_2 .

Restaurant ID	Distance in Km	x	Restaurant ID	Distance in Km	x
135041	4.321		135048	6.381	
132825	4.778		135026	6.651	
132834	5.278		135046	6.761	
132921	5.449		135058	7.157	
132754	5.550		132955	7.557	x_1
135075	5.588		135086	7.894	
132954	5.677		132958	8.400	
132572	5.707		132723	8.552	
135080	6.267		135034	8.662	x_2

Table 3: Values of x_1 and x_2

Finally, we write the criteria function g_{13} associated with the distance attribute based on equation (6):

$$g_{13}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq x_1 \\ \frac{x_2 - x}{x_2 - x_1} & \text{if } x_1 \leq x \leq x_2 \\ 0 & \text{if } x > x_2 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 7.557 \\ \frac{8.662 - x}{1.105} & \text{if } 7.557 \leq x \leq 8.662 \\ 0 & \text{if } x > 8.662 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Each of the 66 restaurants in the subset P_m was evaluated with the above criteria. The results of said evaluation are partially presented in [Tab. 4].

Alt	g_1	g_2	g_3	g_4	g_5	g_6	g_7	g_8	g_9	g_{10}	g_{11}	g_{12}	g_{13}
1	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.111	0.500	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.556	0.222	0.444	0.167	0.065
2	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.333	0.333	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.444	0.056	0.444	0.833	1.000
3	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.556	0.500	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.444	0.222	0.111	0.833	1.000
4	0.667	0.000	0.111	0.556	0.333	0.889	0.722	0.111	0.444	0.000	0.444	0.833	1.000
5	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.556	0.333	0.889	0.722	0.111	0.444	0.056	0.111	0.833	1.000
6	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.333	0.333	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.444	0.000	0.444	0.333	1.000
61	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.556	0.167	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.556	0.000	0.111	0.833	1.000
62	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.556	0.500	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.556	0.056	0.111	0.833	1.000
63	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.556	0.500	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.444	0.056	0.056	0.833	1.000
64	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.556	0.500	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.444	0.056	0.444	0.167	1.000
65	0.222	0.000	0.889	0.111	0.500	0.889	0.722	0.111	0.556	0.222	0.111	0.833	1.000
66	0.667	0.833	0.889	0.333	0.333	0.889	0.722	0.889	0.444	0.056	0.444	0.833	1.000

Table 4: Table of performance of alternatives in each criterion. Own elaboration

6.4.2 Criteria Weights

Each criterion $g_k \in G$ has an associated weight that symbolizes the relative importance of the criterion g_k within the set of criteria G [Figueira et al., 2013]. The weights are denoted by $w_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and are assumed to be positive, and their sum equals 1, that is, $w_k > 0$ for each $g_k \in G$, and $\sum_{g_k \in G} w_k = 1$.

To determine the weights of the criteria, we can define a quotient J_g that compares the Shannon entropy [Zhong and Liu, 2004] present in the values of each criterion g_k in the subset P_m^2 with the entropy of the values of the same criterion g_k in the set P_m .

Entropy is a non-negative function and can be understood as a measure of the information content or uncertainty about a random variable a that takes values of V_a . The entropy reaches the maximum value $\log_2 |V_a|$ for the uniform distribution, that is, $probability(v) = 1/|V_a|$ for every $v \in V_a$.

The minimum entropy value 0 is obtained when the distribution is centered on a particular value v_0 . The entropy value represents the structure or diversity of a probability distribution. A lower value indicates higher structure.

If a criterion has a lower entropy value, we can say that the distribution of its values is unequal in the subset P_m^2 . Therefore, the criteria may be more informative in predicting whether a restaurant belongs to P_m^2 . On the other hand, a criterion with a higher entropy is less informative since the criteria values are more evenly distributed in P_m^2 [Zhong and Liu, 2004]. For a more informative attribute, we would expect it to show less structuring in P_m what in P_m^2 .

We can calculate the quotient J_g using the following formula:

$$J_g = \frac{\mathcal{E}_g^{P_m} - \mathcal{E}_g^{P_m^2}}{\log_2 |B_{g_k}^{P_m}|} \tag{9}$$

Where $\mathcal{E}_{g_k}^{P_m}$ is the entropy of the criteria values g_k in the set P_m , given by:

$$\mathcal{E}_{g_k}^{P_m} = - \sum_{b \in B} \frac{|z_{P_m}(b)|}{|P_m|} \log_2 \left(\frac{|z_{P_m}(b)|}{|P_m|} \right) \tag{10}$$

And $|z_{P_m}(b)|$ is the cardinality of the subset $z_{P_m}(b)$, defined as:

$$z_{P_m}(b) = \{b \in B_{g_k}^{P_m} : I_{g_k}[g_k(p)] = b, b \in B_{g_k}^{P_m}\} \tag{11}$$

Being $B_{g_k}^{P_m}$ the set of values that takes the decision criteria g_k for the restaurants in the set P_m .

Similarly, we define the entropy of the criteria values g_k in the set $P_m 2$, given by:

$$\mathcal{E}_{g_k}^{P_m 2} = - \sum_{d \in D} \frac{|z_{P_m 2}(d)|}{|P_m 2|} \log_2 \left(\frac{|z_{P_m 2}(d)|}{|P_m 2|} \right) \tag{12}$$

And $|z_{P_m 2}(d)|$ is the cardinality of the subset $z_{P_m 2}(d)$, defined as:

$$z_{P_m 2}(d) = \{d \in D_{g_k}^{P_m 2} : I_{g_k}[g_k(x)] = d, d \in D_{g_k}^{P_m 2}\} \tag{13}$$

Being $D_{g_k}^{P_m 2}$ the set of values that takes the decision criteria g_k for the restaurants of the subset $P_m 2$.

The quotient, $-1 \leq J_m \leq 1$, tells us about the change in entropy values as we go from P_m to $P_m 2$. A positive value suggests that the attribute g_k shows more structuring in $P_m 2$ than in P_m and a negative value indicates the opposite.

In the case of criterion g_{13} , the entropy can be calculated by transforming to a categorical variable for each alternative i , assigning the values a, b and c for $g_{13}^i = 1$, $0 < k_{13}^i < 1$ and $g_{13}^i = 0$. [Tab. 5] shows the values J_g for each decision criterion g_k .

Entropy Quotient	Value	Related Attribute
J₁	-0.03278	alcohol
J₂	0.23244	smoking area
J₃	-0.02532	dress code
J₄	-0.14102	accessibility
J₅	0.03290	price
J₆	-0.14326	ambience
J₇	-0.27672	franchise
J₈	-0.13203	area
J₉	0.00892	accepts card payment
J₁₀	0.19309	cuisine type
J₁₁	0.00088	Opening hours
J₁₂	0.02262	parking
J₁₃	-0.15114	distance

Table 5: Entropy quotients J_g for the criteria g_k

Once the quotients J_g for each criterion have been obtained, they will be pairwise compared using the resistance to change grid proposed by [Rogers et al., 2000]. Still, before performing such comparisons, it is advisable to do a correlation analysis between the criteria and eliminate those that are strongly correlated and only select those that are consistent.

We will create a correlation matrix and identify the criteria with an absolute correlation coefficient above 0.29. [Tab. 6] shows the correlation matrix between criteria, identifying the correlated ones in red:

	g ₁	g ₂	g ₃	g ₄	g ₅	g ₆	g ₇	g ₈	g ₉	g ₁₀	g ₁₁	g ₁₂	g ₁₃
g ₁	1.000	0.288	0.008	0.054	0.297	0.089	0.044	0.064	0.456	0.192	0.022	0.248	0.234
g ₂	0.288	1.000	0.113	0.140	0.189	0.062	0.062	0.286	0.232	0.032	0.182	0.130	0.005
g ₃	0.008	0.113	1.000	0.142	0.128	0.051	0.051	0.160	0.055	0.130	0.035	0.082	0.089
g ₄	0.054	0.140	0.142	1.000	0.170	0.053	0.053	0.075	0.091	0.129	0.162	0.058	0.185
g ₅	0.297	0.189	0.128	0.170	1.000	0.060	0.044	0.064	0.387	0.225	0.080	0.318	0.016
g ₆	0.089	0.062	0.051	0.053	0.060	1.000	0.031	0.045	0.171	0.023	0.045	0.172	0.055
g ₇	0.044	0.062	0.051	0.053	0.044	0.031	1.000	0.326	0.182	0.097	0.160	0.244	0.170
g ₈	0.064	0.286	0.160	0.075	0.064	0.045	0.326	1.000	0.008	0.075	0.009	0.060	0.079
g ₉	0.456	0.232	0.055	0.091	0.387	0.171	0.182	0.008	1.000	0.158	0.150	0.377	0.086
g ₁₀	0.192	0.032	0.130	0.129	0.225	0.023	0.097	0.075	0.158	1.000	0.300	0.132	0.018
g ₁₁	0.022	0.182	0.035	0.162	0.080	0.045	0.160	0.009	0.150	0.300	1.000	0.308	0.078
g ₁₂	0.248	0.130	0.082	0.058	0.318	0.172	0.244	0.060	0.377	0.132	0.308	1.000	0.072
g ₁₃	0.234	0.005	0.089	0.185	0.016	0.055	0.170	0.079	0.086	0.018	0.078	0.072	1.000

Table 6: Correlation matrix between criteria. Own elaboration

Once the correlated criteria have been identified, we will create a table indicating the criteria to which each is related and the number of correlated ones. They will be ordered in descending order according to their number of correlates, as shown in [Tab. 7]:

Criteria	Correlated	# of Correlated
g ₂		0
g ₃		0
g ₄		0
g ₆		0
g ₁₃		0
g ₇	g ₈	1
g ₈	g ₇	1
g ₁₀	g ₁₁	1
g ₁	g ₅ , g ₉	2
g ₁₁	g ₁₀ , g ₁₂	2
g ₅	g ₁ , g ₉ , g ₁₂	3
g ₉	g ₁ , g ₅ , g ₁₂	3
g ₁₂	g ₅ , g ₉ , g ₁₁	3

Table 7: Ordered criteria in descending order according to their number of correlates. Own elaboration

Criteria not correlated with others are selected by default; these are g_2, g_3, g_4, g_6 and g_{13} .

In the case of the criteria that are correlated, they will be evaluated in order as follows: if the coefficient J_g of the criterion in the column 1 is greater than or equal to the maximum coefficient J_g of the criteria in the column 2, the criteria in the column 2 will be eliminated, and the column 1 criterion is selected; Otherwise, the column 1 criterion is eliminated and the evaluation of the next row continues. The process is repeated until no more criteria are eliminated or selected.

According to [Tab. 7] and the previously described procedure, the selected criteria are $g_2, g_3, g_4, g_5, g_6, g_8, g_{10}$ and g_{13} . To confirm that they are not correlated, we regenerate the correlation matrix for the selected criteria:

	g2	g3	g4	g5	g6	g8	g10	g13
g2	1	0.113	0.14	0.189	0.062	0.286	0.032	0.005
g3	0.113	1	0.142	0.128	0.051	0.16	0.13	0.089
g4	0.14	0.142	1	0.17	0.053	0.075	0.129	0.185
g5	0.189	0.128	0.17	1	0.06	0.064	0.225	0.016
g6	0.062	0.051	0.053	0.06	1	0.045	0.023	0.055
g8	0.286	0.16	0.075	0.064	0.045	1	0.075	0.079
g10	0.032	0.13	0.129	0.225	0.023	0.075	1	0.018
g13	0.005	0.089	0.185	0.016	0.055	0.079	0.018	1

Table 8: Correlation matrix of selected criteria. Own elaboration

Now that we have not correlated criteria, they will be compared in pairs using the resistance to change grid proposed by [Rogers et al., 2000], taking the following rules as reference:

If we have two different criteria g and g' , and are their respective indices J_g and $J_{g'}$, then:

- a) If $J_g > J_{g'}$, the criteria will be considered g more resistant to change than criteria g' , and will be marked in the table with a 1.
- b) If $J_g = J_{g'}$, the criteria will be considered to g be equally resistant to change as the criteria g' , and will be marked in the table with the letter E .
- c) If $J_g < J_{g'}$, the criteria will be considered g' more resistant to change than criteria g , and will be marked in the table with a letter X .

Subsequently, the number of ones you had in each row and the number of ones X that you had in each column will be added to each criterion, and then one will be added. Finally, we will obtain the weights w_k by normalizing these scores for each criterion. [Tab. 9] presents the resistance to changing the grid for the set of criteria G .

Resistance to change grid												
Criteria	Criteria Jg Quotient	g2	g3	g4	g5	g6	g8	g10	g13	Resistance to change	RTC+1	w_k
g2	0.232	---	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	7	8	0.22222
g3	-0.025	---	---	1	X	1	1	X	1	4	5	0.13889
g4	-0.141	---	---	---	X	1	X	X	1	2	3	0.08333
g5	0.033	---	---	---	---	1	1	X	1	5	6	0.16667
g6	-0.143	---	---	---	---	---	X	X	1	1	2	0.05556
g8	-0.132	---	---	---	---	---	---	X	1	3	4	0.11111
g10	0.193	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	1	6	7	0.19444
g13	-0.151	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0	1	0.02778

Table 9: Resistance to change grid and w_k criteria weights g_k

6.4.3 Thresholds

Additionally, it is necessary to specify the indifference $q_k(p_i)$, preference $p_k(p_i)$, and veto thresholds $v_k(p_i)$ for each criterion $g_k \in G$.

To calculate the thresholds required by the ELECTRE III method in this case study, the preference, indifference, and veto thresholds will be expressed as a percentage of the average performance of each criterion, as proposed by [Baseer et al., 2023]. This method is chosen due to practical considerations such as the possible systematization of the targeted marketing model, the impossibility of requesting thresholds from clients, and the cognitive challenge that their determination may represent for the owner of the problem. The thresholds can be easily modified through the adjustment parameter γ .

The indifference threshold is:

$$q_k = \gamma_q \cdot \mu_k \tag{14}$$

where:

- $\gamma_q = 5\%$
- μ_k represents the average performance of all alternatives for a given criterion, defined by:

$$\mu_k = \mu(g_k) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{|P_m 1|} g_k(p_i^1)}{|P_m 1|} \tag{15}$$

where $g_k(p_i^1)$ are the values the decision criteria take g_k for each restaurant in the subset $P_m 1$.

The preference threshold is:

$$p_k = \gamma_p \cdot \mu_k \tag{16}$$

with $\gamma_p = 15\%$.

And finally, the veto threshold is:

$$v_k = \gamma_v \cdot \mu_k \tag{17}$$

with $\gamma_v = 30\%$.

With this information, it is now possible to define the thresholds of indifference (I_k), strict preference (P_k), and weak preference (Q_k) for each criterion $g_k \in G$.

In the case of the veto threshold, it is necessary to analyze the problem to determine which criteria a veto should be used. In this particular problem, it was decided to use a veto only in the criterion g_3 associated with the dress code attribute; this is because, in general, it may be undesirable for a customer to attend a restaurant that restricts entry if one does not have formal attire, such as it can be observed in the particular case of the user U1061 who did not visit any restaurant with that dress code. [Tab. 10] shows the weights and thresholds of indifference, preference and veto for each criterion g_k .

Table of weights and thresholds								
	<i>g2</i>	<i>g3</i>	<i>g4</i>	<i>g5</i>	<i>g6</i>	<i>g8</i>	<i>g10</i>	<i>g13</i>
w_k	0.14286	0.06593	0.03297	0.10989	0.02198	0.04396	0.13187	0.12088
q_k	0.03068	0.04142	0.02409	0.01844	0.04327	0.04209	0.00321	0.04599
p_k	0.09203	0.12426	0.07226	0.05531	0.12981	0.12627	0.00963	0.13797
v_k	---	0.24852	---	---	---	---	---	---

Table 10: Weights and thresholds including veto

6.5 Fuzzy Outranking Matrix

Applying the ELECTRE III method, we construct an outranking relation. Obtaining the fuzzy outranking matrix is shown partially in [Tab. 11].

Fuzzy Outranking Matrix														
Restaurant_ID	Restaurant_ID Alternatives	132755	132830	132845	132846	132847	132851	...	135079	135081	135082	135085	135106	135108
		1	2	3	4	5	6	...	61	62	63	64	65	66
132755	1	1	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	...	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.55	0.52
132830	2	0.43	1	0.4	0.64	0.64	0.67	...	0.64	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.43	0.67
132845	3	0.67	0.67	1	0.67	0.67	0.67	...	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67
132846	4	0	0	0	1	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0
132847	5	0.38	0.63	0.38	0.67	1	0.63	...	0.63	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.43	0.63
132851	6	0.43	0.54	0.4	0.64	0.51	1	...	0.64	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.43	0.54
...
135079	61	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.56	0.43	0.56	...	1	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43
135081	62	0.54	0.67	0.54	0.67	0.67	0.67	...	0.67	1	0.67	0.67	0.54	0.67
135082	63	0.54	0.67	0.54	0.67	0.67	0.67	...	0.67	0.67	1	0.67	0.54	0.67
135085	64	0.54	0.67	0.54	0.67	0.67	0.67	...	0.67	0.67	0.67	1	0.54	0.67
135106	65	0.48	0.45	0.45	0.64	0.49	0.45	...	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	1	0.45
135108	66	0.43	0.67	0.4	0.64	0.64	0.67	...	0.64	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.43	1

Table 11: Fuzzy outranking matrix

6.6 Exploiting the Outranking Relation

The second phase of the method uses the fuzzy outranking matrix to determine the global ranking of products based on decreasing preference. The net flow rule (NFR) is applied [Brans et al., 1986] [Behzadian et al., 2010]. [Tab. 12] shows the flows for each of the alternatives in the subset P_m as well as the final ranking.

ALTERNATIVES RANKING											
Restaurant_ID	Alternatives	F(+)	F(-)	Net Flow	Ranking	Restaurant_ID	Alternatives	F(+)	F(-)	Net Flow	Ranking
135025	24	43.55	25.91	17.64	1	135064	51	36.71	34.04	2.67	14
135027	25	43.55	25.91	17.64	1	135076	60	36.71	34.04	2.67	14
135028	26	43.55	25.91	17.64	1	132854	7	35.90	33.25	2.65	15
132845	3	43.55	25.91	17.64	1	132866	12	35.90	33.25	2.65	15
132925	21	42.14	26.32	15.82	2	135033	29	35.69	33.30	2.39	16
132869	13	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	135038	31	35.69	33.30	2.39	17
135060	48	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	135071	56	35.69	33.30	2.39	17
135062	49	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	135106	65	29.72	29.25	0.47	18
135063	50	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	135055	45	31.97	31.75	0.22	19
135070	55	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	132870	14	33.79	34.39	-0.60	20
135072	57	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	132937	22	29.68	30.97	-1.29	21
135081	62	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	132851	6	32.38	34.79	-2.41	22
135082	63	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	132856	8	32.38	34.79	-2.41	22
135085	64	41.99	30.74	11.25	3	132858	9	32.38	34.79	-2.41	22
135069	54	38.99	27.97	11.02	4	135039	32	32.17	34.84	-2.67	23
132872	15	40.10	31.24	8.86	5	135051	41	32.17	34.84	-2.67	23
135057	46	36.21	28.98	7.23	6	132884	18	29.51	33.43	-3.92	24
135059	47	36.21	28.98	7.23	6	135079	61	32.03	36.15	-4.12	25
132755	1	34.22	27.06	7.16	7	135032	28	31.01	35.39	-4.38	26
135042	34	37.31	32.85	4.46	8	132861	10	28.35	33.48	-5.13	27
135043	35	37.31	32.85	4.46	8	135047	38	30.41	36.60	-6.19	28
135044	36	37.31	32.85	4.46	8	135065	52	30.41	36.60	-6.19	28
132830	2	37.06	32.69	4.37	9	135066	53	30.41	36.60	-6.19	28
132877	17	37.06	32.69	4.37	9	135073	58	30.41	36.60	-6.19	28
132885	19	37.06	32.69	4.37	9	132875	16	27.45	36.72	-9.27	29
135108	66	37.06	32.69	4.37	10	135074	59	25.73	38.69	-12.96	30
132847	5	35.88	32.41	3.47	11	135035	30	18.23	38.93	-20.70	31
135030	27	36.03	32.89	3.14	12	135053	43	17.97	39.41	-21.44	32
135049	39	34.52	31.49	3.03	13	132951	23	2.51	35.17	-32.66	33

135040	33	36.71	34.04	2.67	14	135045	37	2.35	36.65	-34.30	34
135050	40	36.71	34.04	2.67	14	132922	20	1.96	36.44	-34.48	35
135052	42	36.71	34.04	2.67	14	132862	11	1.90	39.51	-37.61	36
135054	44	36.71	34.04	2.67	14	132846	4	1.56	40.18	-38.62	37

Table 12: Final ranking of alternatives

6.7 Cut-Off Point

To conclude, the decision maker must choose a cut-off point from which the products to be recommended will be selected. The cut point is problem-dependent all products above the cut point will be promoted to the customer. In the case of recommending restaurants to the user $U1061$, it has been decided to choose the five restaurants that top the ranking, shown in [Tab. 13].

RECOMMENDED RESTAURANTS					
Restaurant ID	Alternative	F(+)	F(-)	Net Flow	Ranking
135025	24	43.55	25.91	17.64	1
135027	25	43.55	25.91	17.64	1
135028	26	43.55	25.91	17.64	1
132845	3	43.55	25.91	17.64	1
132925	21	42.14	26.32	15.82	2

Table 13: Restaurants to recommend to user $U1061$

6.8 Conclusion to the Case Study

Conducting this case study using the proposed customer-oriented targeted marketing model enabled a restaurant recommendation to be made by modeling a user's preferences of an online restaurant guide. The preferences of the restaurants were evaluated using the fuzzy outranking relation method known as ELECTRE III. The results were further analyzed using the fuzzy outranking relation through the net flow rule to create a ranking of the restaurants in order of decreasing preference. The restaurants that topped the ranking were those selected to be recommended to the user $U1061$.

7 Conclusion

This research paper introduces a framework for solving customer-oriented marketing problems using multiple criteria. Our approach is based on the outranking method, where a set of criteria is used to determine the most suitable products for a customer through pairwise comparisons. The proposed algorithmic framework identifies the k -most preferable products (k -MPP) from a set of products under consideration for targeted marketing. We use customer and product attributes and transaction data to construct outranking relationships that reflect the preferences between a customer and a product. This framework employs preference relations to solve the customer-oriented marketing problem.

By adopting a customer-oriented marketing strategy, we can gain a significant advantage in understanding our customers' preferences. This approach involves

creating criteria based on customer preferences, allowing us to personalize product recommendations and launch targeted marketing campaigns.

We plan to expand our framework for customer-oriented targeted marketing in the future. We aim to construct outranking relations related to a group of customers who share similar preferences. To strengthen our results, we plan to conduct experiments. Specifically, we want to apply our approach to a customer-oriented marketing strategy considering a group of customers. Moreover, our work assumes that each criterion is neither predominant nor negligible. Still, we plan to investigate an outranking approach that does not consider the weight of the criteria when there is not enough evidence to suggest that some criteria are more important than others. Finally, we also plan to expand the application of our framework across various knowledge domains.

Acknowledges

This paper is partly funded by the Red iberoamericana de inteligencia artificial y analítica de datos 523RT0147.

References

- [Adomavicius and Tuzhilin, 2005] Adomavicius, G., Tuzhilin, A.: "Toward the next generation of recommender systems: a survey of the state-of-the-art and possible extensions"; *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 17, 6 (2005), 734–749, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2005.99>
- [Alves Gomes and Meisen, 2023] Alves Gomes, M., Meisen, T.: "A review on customer segmentation methods for personalized customer targeting in e-commerce use cases"; *Information Systems and E-Business Management*, 21, 3 (2023), 527–570, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10257-023-00640-4>
- [Baseer et al., 2023] Baseer, M., Ghiaus, C., Viala, R., Gauthier, N., Daniel, S.: "pELECTRE-Tri: Probabilistic ELECTRE-Tri Method—Application for the Energy Renovation of Buildings"; *Energies*, 16, 14 (2023), 5296, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16145296>
- [Behzadian et al., 2010] Behzadian, M., Kazemzadeh, R. B., Albadvi, A., Aghdasi, M.: "PROMETHEE: A comprehensive literature review on methodologies and applications"; *European Journal of Operational Research*, 200, 1 (2010), 198–215, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2009.01.021>
- [Bijmolt et al., 2021] Bijmolt, T. H. A., Broekhuis, M., De Leeuw, S., Hirche, C., Rooderkerk, R. P., Sousa, R., Zhu, S. X.: "Challenges at the marketing–operations interface in omni-channel retail environments"; *Journal of Business Research*, 122 (2021), 864–874, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.11.034>
- [Brans et al., 1986] Brans, J. P., Vincke, Ph., Mareschal, B.: "How to select and how to rank projects: The Promethee method"; *European Journal of Operational Research*, 24, 2 (1986), 228–238, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217\(86\)90044-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217(86)90044-5)

- [Camilleri, 2018] Camilleri, M. A.: "Market Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning"; In M. Camilleri, Travel Marketing, Tourism Economics and the Airline Product; Springer International Publishing, Cham (2018), 69–83, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-49849-2_4
- [Ferguson et al., 2021] Ferguson, C. Y., Paramita, H., Ratnasari, I.: "Relationship Marketing Activities in Building Customer-Oriented Marketing Services"; Kanal: Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi, 9, 2 (2021), 65–69, <https://doi.org/10.21070/kanal.v9i2.1014>
- [Figueira et al., 2013] Figueira, J. R., Greco, S., Roy, B., Słowiński, R.: "An Overview of ELECTRE Methods and their Recent Extensions"; Journal of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis, 20, 1–2 (2013), 61–85, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mcda.1482>
- [Hao et al., 2020] Hao, J., Zhao, T., Li, J., Dong, X. L., Faloutsos, C., Sun, Y., Wang, W.: "P-Companion: A Principled Framework for Diversified Complementary Product Recommendation"; Proc. of the 29th ACM International Conference on Information & Knowledge Management; ACM, Virtual Event Ireland (2020), 2517–2524, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3340531.3412732>
- [Huang et al., 2005] Huang, J., Zhong, N., Yao, Y. Y., Liu, C.: "A General Framework of Targeted Marketing"; In P. S. Szczepaniak, J. Kacprzyk & A. Niewiadomski (Eds.), Advances in Web Intelligence (Vol. 3528); Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2005), 197–203, https://doi.org/10.1007/11495772_31
- [Huang et al., 2014] Huang, J., Zhong, N., Yao, Y.: "A Unified Framework of Targeted Marketing Using Customer Preferences"; Computational Intelligence, 30, 3 (2014), 451–472, <https://doi.org/10.1111/coin.12003>
- [Islam and Liu, 2016] Islam, Md. S., Liu, C.: "Know your customer: computing k-most promising products for targeted marketing"; The VLDB Journal, 25, 4 (2016), 545–570, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00778-016-0428-3>
- [Ivan Franko et al., 2021] Ivan Franko, Tatomyr, I., Kvasnii, Z., Precarpathian Institute named of M. Hrushevsky of Interregional Academy of Personnel Management: "Artificial intelligence as a basis for the development of the digital economy"; (1st ed.); OKTAN PRINT s.r.o. (2021), <https://doi.org/10.46489/aiabftd-07>
- [Javed et al., 2021] Javed, U., Shaukat, K., Hameed, I. A., Iqbal, F., Mahboob Alam, T., Luo, S.: "A Review of Content-Based and Context-Based Recommendation Systems"; International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET), 16, 03 (2021), 274, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i03.18851>
- [Ling and Li, 1998] Ling, C. X., Li, C.: "Data Mining for Direct Marketing: Problems and Solutions"; Proc. of KDD'98 – Fourth International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining; AAAI Press (1998)
- [Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2024] Pérez-Almaguer, Y., Carballo-Cruz, E., Caballero-Mota, Y., Yera, R.: "Exploring content-based group recommendation for suggesting restaurants in Havana City"; JUCS - Journal of Universal Computer Science, 30, 1 (2024), 106–129, <https://doi.org/10.3897/jucs.104838>

[Rogers et al., 2000] Rogers, M., Bruen, M., Maystre, L.-Y.: "ELECTRE and Decision Support: Methods and Applications in Engineering and Infrastructure Investment"; Springer US, Boston, MA (2000), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-5057-7>

[Rosário and Raimundo, 2021] Rosário, A., Raimundo, R.: "Consumer Marketing Strategy and E-Commerce in the Last Decade: A Literature Review"; *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16, 7 (2021), 3003–3024, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16070164>

[Roy, 1996] Roy, B.: "Multicriteria Methodology for Decision Aiding"; Springer US, Boston, MA (1996), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-2500-1>

[Sarkar and De Bruyn, 2021] Sarkar, M., De Bruyn, A.: "LSTM Response Models for Direct Marketing Analytics: Replacing Feature Engineering with Deep Learning"; *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 53 (2021), 80–95, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2020.07.002>

[Shambour et al., 2023] Shambour, Q. Y., Abualhaj, M. M., Abu-Shareha, A. A.: "Restaurant Recommendations Based on Multicriteria Recommendation Algorithm"; *JUCS - Journal of Universal Computer Science*, 29, 2 (2023), 179–200, <https://doi.org/10.3897/jucs.78240>

[Vargas et al., 2011] Vargas, B., González, G., Ponce, R.: "Effects of relevant contextual features in the performance of a restaurant recommender system"; *Proc. of the 3rd Workshop on Context-Aware Recommender Systems (CARS 2011)*; Chicago, Illinois, USA (2011)

[Villegas et al., 2018] Villegas, N. M., Sánchez, C., Díaz-Cely, J., Tamura, G.: "Characterizing context-aware recommender systems: A systematic literature review"; *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 140 (2018), 173–200, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2017.11.003>

[Yang et al., 2023] Yang, T., Xu, Z., Ai, Q.: "Vertical Allocation-based Fair Exposure Amortizing in Ranking"; *Proc. of the Annual International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval in the Asia Pacific Region*; (2023), 234–244, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3624918.3625313>

[Zhong and Liu, 2004] Zhong, N., Liu, J.: "Intelligent Technologies for Information Analysis"; Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2004), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-07952-2>